

Post Orthodontic Stability: Role of Retainer type and Duration

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Abstract

Aim: To evaluate post-orthodontic stability in relation to retainer type and duration of wear, and to assess whether combined retention offers advantages over single retainer protocols.¹

Materials and Methods: The study was carried out at the Department of Orthodontics, Subharti Dental College, Meerut. A cross-sectional questionnaire based survey was conducted using a structured Google Form. A total of 94 completed responses were analyzed descriptively using percentage distribution.

Results: Most respondents were aged 18–25 years (90.4%) male and female (68.1%). Dental students comprised of the largest group (66%), followed by orthodontic patients (13.8%) and general dentists (9.6%). Among participants, 41.5% had undergone orthodontic treatment, predominantly with metal braces (45.7%). Treatment duration was typically less than two years. Retainer compliance was poor: although 21.3% reported fixed retainers and 18.1% clear thermoplastic retainers, 38.3% never wore one and only 18.1% used retainers daily. Advice on retention duration varied, with most instructed to wear retainers for less than two years, while lifelong retention was rarely recommended (6.4%). Post-treatment outcomes showed that 31.9% experienced significant tooth shifting, while satisfaction with dental alignment was mixed (57.4% satisfied, 33% neutral). Retainer-related problems were common, particularly discomfort (26.6%) and breakage (14.9%). Clinicians reported oral hygiene issues (39.1%) and poor compliance (21.7%) as major challenges.

Discussion: This survey underscores that post-orthodontic relapse remains a common clinical concern, with many respondents reporting noticeable tooth movement after treatment. Poor retainer compliance emerged as a key factor, as only a minority wore retainers daily despite awareness of their importance. Even among dental students, adherence was suboptimal, suggesting that knowledge alone does not ensure compliance and highlighting the need for sustained motivation and follow-up. Communication gaps were evident, with several respondents unsure of their retainer type, while clear thermoplastic retainers, though esthetically preferred, were frequently associated with discomfort and breakage. Oral hygiene issues were the most frequent challenge with fixed retainers, reflecting their known association with plaque accumulation and periodontal complications.

The wide variation in advised retention duration illustrates the absence of standardized guidelines, with few patients instructed on prolonged or lifelong retention despite growing evidence supporting extended use. Moderate satisfaction with dental alignment further suggests that even minor post treatment changes can affect patient perception of success. Overall, these findings emphasize the importance of clear retention protocols, improved patient education, and individualized long-term planning to optimize orthodontic stability and patient satisfaction.

Conclusion: This study highlights poor long-term compliance with retainer use and variability in retention advice, contributing to post-treatment instability. Greater emphasis on patient education, standardized retention protocols, and strategies to improve adherence are essential to optimize orthodontic outcomes.

Introduction

Orthodontics aims to correct irregular bites and provide functional dental alignment². Orthodontic treatment seeks to establish an optimal occlusal relationship that ensures functional harmony among the dentition, temporomandibular joint, and neuromuscular system³. Ensuring long-term stability of orthodontic outcomes remains a fundamental objective in clinical practice. The application of fixed or removable retention devices plays a critical role in minimizing post-treatment relapse⁴.

Post orthodontic retention is considered one of the most debated topics in orthodontics. This stage of treatment focuses on keeping teeth in their new, corrected positions once active movement has finished. While retention is necessary for nearly every patient, there is little consensus on the best

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method to use for each case. If retention is not carried out, teeth often drift back toward their original alignment. Retention can be carried out using either removable or fixed retainers. There is no universally agreed length of time for retention, but research shows that the fibres around teeth need at least about 232 days to adapt to their new positions. Even after this period, teeth may still shift back over time. Because of this risk of relapse, many orthodontists choose to keep retainers in place for extended periods, and in some cases, indefinitely⁵. Therefore effective retention planning is critical in long-term orthodontic care.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in the Orthodontics Department of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopaedics at Subharti Dental College and Hospital, Meerut, and used questionnaires to explore how different retainers and the duration of time they are worn affecting the stability of orthodontic results. Participants included were orthodontically treated patients who had completed active treatment and were currently wearing retainers or had previously completed the retention phase.

Study Population and Sample Size

A total of 94 completed responses were included in the final analysis. The majority of respondents belonged to the 18–25-year age group, and the study population comprised dental students, orthodontic patients, general dentists, and other respondents, providing a broad overview of retention related perceptions.

Inclusion Criteria

- Individuals who completed fixed orthodontic treatment.
- Age range between 18to35 years
- Patients willing to participate and able to provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients undergoing active orthodontic treatment.
- Individuals with syndromic conditions or craniofacial anomalies affecting occlusion or stability.
- Unwilling or non-consenting participants.

Survey Instrument

Data was collected using a structured questionnaire created using Google Forms. The questionnaire consisted of closed ended and multiple choice items covering:

- Demographic information
- History of orthodontic treatment
- Type of retainer prescribed
- Duration of retention
- Daily compliance (for removable retainers)
- Patient-reported stability, relapse, or shifting
- Satisfaction and challenges related to retainer use

Ethical Considerations

Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained electronically prior to questionnaire submission. Participant anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained throughout the study.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were entered into a spreadsheet and analyzed using descriptive statistical methods. Results were expressed as frequencies and percentage distributions. The findings were presented using tables and graphical representations, including pie charts, to facilitate clear interpretation of the data.

Results

Study design and sample characteristics

This cross-sectional questionnaire based survey was conducted in accordance with the Materials and Methods described earlier. A total

of 94 completed responses were included for analysis. Data were collected using a structured Google Form and analysed descriptively using percentage distribution.

Most respondents belonged to the 18–25year age group (90.4%), reflecting a young study population. Females constituted 68.1% of respondents, males constituted 30.9%, and a very small proportion preferred not to disclose gender. Regarding respondent profile, dental students formed the largest group (66%), followed by orthodontic patients (13.8%) and general dentists (9.6%).

Variable	Category	Percentage
Age	<18 years	4.3
	18-25 years	90.4
	26-35 years	5.3
Gender	Male	30.9
	Female	68.1
	Prefer not to say	1.0
Respondent type	Dental Student	66.0
	Orthodontic Patient	13.8
	General Dentists	9.6
	Others	10.6

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of respondents (n = 94)

Orthodontic Treatment details

Among all respondents, 41.5% had undergone orthodontic treatment, while 58.5% had not orthodontic treatment. Among treated individuals, metal braces were the most commonly used appliance (45.7%), followed by self-ligating appliances (13.8%), ceramic braces (6.4%), and clear aligners (8.5%).

Treatment duration was reported as less than one year by 50%, 1–2 years by 34%, 2–3 years by 13.8%, and more than three years by a small minority 2.2%.

Figure 1. Distribution of type of orthodontic appliance used Pie chart depicting the proportion of metal braces, ceramic braces, self-ligating appliances, clear aligners and other response.

Retainer type and Compliance

Regarding retention, 21.3% reported wearing fixed/bonded retainers, while 10.6% used Hawley retainers, 18.1% clear thermo-plastic retainers, and 42.6% were unsure of the retainer type.

Only 18.1% of respondents wore their retainer daily, whereas

10.6% wore it occasionally. A considerable proportion (33%) stopped wearing retainers after the prescribed period, and 38.3% reported never wearing a retainer, indicating poor long-term compliance.

Figure 2. Type of retainer worn by respondents Pie chart showing distribution of fixed, removable and uncertain retainer types.

Figure 3. Current retainer wearing status Pie chart illustrating daily, occasional, discontinued and non-users of retainers.

Duration advised for retention

Advice regarding retention duration varied considerably. 24.5% were advised less than 6 months, 23.4% for 6 months–1 year, 27.7% for 1–2 years, and only 6.4% were advised lifelong retention.

Figure 4. Duration for which retainer wear was advised.

Post-treatment stability and satisfaction

When asked about post-treatment tooth movement, 31.9% reported significant shifting, 25.5% slight shifting, while 11.7% noticed no change and 30.9% were unsure.

Satisfaction with current dental alignment showed mixed responses. 23.4% strongly agreed and 34% agreed that they were satisfied, 33% remained neutral, while a smaller proportion expressed dissatisfaction.

Figure 5. Perceived tooth movement after orthodontic treatment.

Figure 6. Satisfaction with current dental alignment

Retainer related problems and clinical challenges

More than half of the respondents experienced retainer-related problems. Discomfort (26.6%) was the most common issue, followed by breakage (14.9%), poor fit (7.4%), and staining (6.4%).

From the clinician perspective, the most frequently observed challenges were oral hygiene issues (39.1%), poor compliance (21.7%), retainer loss (13%), and relapse despite retention (12%).

Issue	Percentage
Oral Hygiene Issues	39.1
Poor Compliance	21.7
Retainer Loss	13.0
Relapse Despite Retention	12.0
Breakage	8.7

Table 2. Common retainer-related problems and challenges

Discussion

The present cross-sectional questionnaire based survey evaluated awareness, practices, and experiences related to orthodontic retention among a predominantly young population, with the majority of respondents belonging to the 18–25-year age group. The findings revealed considerable variability in retainer type usage, duration of retention advised, and patient compliance. A large proportion of participants were uncertain about the type of retainer provided after orthodontic treatment, and long-term compliance was notably poor, with many respondents discontinuing retainer use after the prescribed period or never wearing a retainer at all. Advice regarding retention duration was inconsistent, with most respondents being instructed to wear retainers for short-term periods and only a small proportion advised lifelong retention. A significant number of respondents reported post-treatment tooth movement ranging from slight to marked shifting, accompanied by moderate levels of satisfaction with current dental alignment. Retainer related issues such as discomfort, breakage, and poor fit were commonly experienced, while clinicians identified oral hygiene problems, poor compliance, retainer loss, and relapse despite retention as frequent challenges. These findings reflect existing gaps in patient awareness and adherence to retention protocols, which may adversely affect long-term orthodontic stability. Retention has long been recognized as an essential phase of orthodontic treatment, as post-treatment changes may occur long after appliance removal. A Cochrane systematic review by Littlewood et al. highlighted that relapse is common and that retention is critical for maintaining treatment outcomes¹. This supports the occurrence of post-treatment tooth movement reported by participants in the present study. Kartal and Kaya further emphasized that post-orthodontic changes are inevitable and that retainers play a crucial role in preserving alignment, favouring long-term retention strategies². However, despite this strong evidence, the present study demonstrated limited compliance and short retention durations advised, reflecting an unfavourable deviation from established recommendations.

Pattanaik et al. reported that effective retention protocols significantly influence the stability of orthodontic outcomes, reinforcing the need for sustained retainer use³. Bonadio et al. also noted that long-term stability depends not only on orthodontic mechanics but also on post-treatment management strategies. In contrast, the present study revealed inconsistent retention advice and poor patient adherence, which may explain the high prevalence of perceived relapse.

The absence of universally accepted retention protocols has been widely reported. Knaup et al. demonstrated that even with fixed retainers, additional removable retainers may be required to improve stability, suggesting that retention strategies should be individualized. Similarly, Littlewood et al. reported insufficient high-quality evidence to support a single ideal retention approach. These findings may explain the wide variation in retention duration advised to participants in the present study, although such variability may negatively influence long-term stability.

Fixed retainers are widely advocated for maintaining post-treatment alignment, particularly in the mandibular anterior region. Bearn highlighted that bonded retainers eliminate patient compliance issues and are therefore advantageous for long-term stability. Renkema et al. reported a strong preference for fixed retainers among orthodontists to ensure mandibular anterior alignment. Pratt et al. similarly observed increasing global adoption of bonded retainers in orthodontic practice.

Despite these favourable findings, the present study showed that only a limited proportion of respondents reported wearing fixed

retainers, while many were unsure of the retainer type provided, indicating a gap between clinician preference reported in the literature and patient reported experience.

Long-term clinical studies have demonstrated favourable outcomes with canine-to-canine bonded retainers. Zachrisson reported reliable long-term stability with directly bonded retainers¹. Renkema et al. further confirmed the effectiveness of canine to canine bonded retainers in maintaining mandibular anterior alignment over extended periods¹¹.

Regarding material selection, Zachrisson emphasized that multi-stranded stainless-steel wires permit physiological tooth movement while reducing stress on bonded teeth¹². Årtun reported acceptable periodontal responses associated with long-term use of such retainers when oral hygiene is maintained¹³. Dahl also supported their durability and clinical reliability¹. In contrast, the present study identified oral hygiene challenges and retainer breakage as common problems, suggesting that the benefits of fixed retainers may be compromised without adequate maintenance and follow-up.

Evidence strongly supports prolonged or lifelong retention. Little et al. demonstrated progressive mandibular anterior crowding even 10–20 years after treatment completion, irrespective of initial treatment success¹. Keim et al. reported a growing trend toward indefinite retention in contemporary orthodontic practice¹. These findings contrast with the present study, where most respondents were advised of short-term retention, an unfavourable practice that may contribute to the high prevalence of post-treatment tooth movement reported. Despite their advantages, fixed retainers are associated with complications. Iliadi et al. reported that retainer failures are common, particularly within the first year¹. Lee identified the adhesive enamel interface as the most frequent site of failure¹. Kučera and Marek described unexpected complications, including unwanted tooth movement, emphasizing the importance of regular monitoring¹. These findings are consistent with the present study, where breakage and relapse despite retention were commonly reported.

Aesthetic alternatives such as fiber-reinforced retainers have shown less favourable outcomes. Tacken et al. reported higher failure rates compared with multistranded wire retainers². Bolla et al. observed increased debonding with long-term use of glass fiber reinforced retainers²¹. Chinvipas et al. further highlighted the risk of enamel fracture associated with repeated rebonding procedures²². These findings support continued preference for conventional multi-stranded wire retainers despite aesthetic limitations.

Periodontal health remains a key concern in long-term retention. Pandis et al. reported increased plaque accumulation around bonded retainers²³. Conversely, Levin et al. emphasized that periodontal changes are largely influenced by oral hygiene rather than retainer presence alone². Booth et al. concluded that permanently bonded retainers do not significantly compromise periodontal health when patients are adequately motivated and regularly followed up². These findings suggest that periodontal risks can be minimized through appropriate patient education and maintenance.

The findings of the present study, when interpreted alongside existing literature, highlight the need for improved patient education regarding the importance of retention, retainer type, and duration of wear. Clinicians should emphasize long-term or lifelong retention, particularly in the mandibular anterior region, and ensure that patients are adequately informed about retainer maintenance and potential complications. Regular follow-up visits are essential to detect early failures, manage oral hygiene challenges, and prevent unintended tooth movement.

Conclusion

Within the limitations of this questionnaire-based survey, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Post-orthodontic relapse or perceived tooth movement is common following active treatment.
2. Long-term retainer compliance is suboptimal, even among individuals with dental education.
3. Discomfort, appliance breakage, and oral hygiene difficulties are major factors affecting continued retainer use.
4. Considerable variation exists in the type and duration of retention protocols advised by clinicians.
5. Individualized, case dependent retention strategies, supported by patient education and regular follow-up, are essential for improving post-orthodontic stability.

Further longitudinal studies with extended follow-up periods are recommended to better assess the long-term effectiveness of different retainer types and retention durations.

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